

Biochemistry as a Frontier Science: An Exploratory Orientation Lecture for Beginners

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Abstract-: Considering the present economic meltdown and the associated uncertainties due to the COVID-19 aftermath in Nigeria and a vast number of unemployed/job seekers among varsity graduates, it became imperative to re-orientate beginners pursuing the discipline of Biochemistry. Through intellectual engagements in various disciplines of Biochemistry, the research aims to explore biochemistry's relevance as a frontier science. The discussion was for one month. The groups discussed the following: Group-1 (Medical Biochemistry), Group-2 (Food Biochemistry), Group-3 (Mechanomedicine), Group-4 (Industrial Biochemistry), and Group-5 (Molecular basis of disease). The discussion outcome of Grps-1 to 5 showed that biochemistry illuminates many areas of medicines reshaping and giving directions to improved healthcare delivery (Grp-1). In nutrition, biochemistry posited nutrition as a cardinal requirement for optimal health (Grp-2). Molecule and cellular response to cells from stimuli as a prospect for cancer treatment and how achieving optimal health is the mechano-medicine approach to health from a biochemical viewpoint (Grp 3). In modern biomedical research, using enzymes in drug design, delivering biosensors, isolating novel proteins, and other industrial products anchored on large-scale enzyme catalyses are all working ideas of biochemistry in industries (Grp-4). Disease has a molecular basis expressed on a biochemical basis. Since diseases cause alteration of biochemical molecules, a biochemical picture of the alteration depicts the presence of disease mechanism (Grp-5). Biochemistry is transformative with pedagogical approaches and experiential learning. It is in all spheres, hence frontier science.

Keywords: Biochemistry, economic recovery, sustainability, enzymes, various aspects of biochemistry

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Received: January 15, 2024

Revised: March 5, 2024

Accepted: March 16, 2024

Cite this Paper as: Nwachukwu, Francis Chukwuedozie" Biochemistry as a Frontier Science: An Exploratory Orientation Lecture for Beginners. *Science Journal of Applied and Natual Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 79-94, 30 March 2024.

About the Journal: SJANS is a multidisciplinary science journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Science, Nigeria Police Academy, Kano, Nigeria

1.0 Introduction

Biochemistry combines two disciplines - Biology and Chemistry (Singh *et al.*, 2004). Biochemists study biochemical reactions that happen at molecular levels. It covers genetics, nutrition, and others. In medical biochemistry, the health and disease of humans are the focal points. Though biochemistry seems to revolve via the structures and functions as biological macromolecules interact, this is a peripheral and shallow representation. Biochemistry is deeper than that.

Like the Medical sciences, Biochemistry is vast in areas of research coverage. It is rapidly evolving, expanding, and reshaping all areas of Science. As the handmaid, it plays a subsidiary role in all fields of life science in any form through practical applications. It is progressive at an unstoppable velocity, and expectation is beyond human imagination. It holds the key to the promises of

the domain of sciences through developing cutting-edge research (Singh *et al.*, 2004).

With the escalation in threat to health via non-communicable diseases, environmental pollutants, climate change, antibiotic resistance, and influencers, there is a need to uncover the cause of pathologies on cellular levels, which is hugely important, and research in biochemistry is a match. Research in biochemistry is more crucial than ever as it is a game changer and a handle for economic recovery. Findings in biochemistry posit Biochemistry as a frontier discipline in crafting an idea in cutting-edge technology, and by extension, it facilitates access to frontier research in Basic Sciences through synthesizing ideas that seem invaluable to catapult advancements in developmental novelty and resultant economic development, particularly in a world where knowledge impacts more on the economy (Iaria *et al.*, 2018). Lucrative areas for graduates in biochemistry are less explored, making many holders engage in unskilled Jobs.

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

Advancing the knowledge aspects of biochemistry and employability, the teaming graduates require an expert proficient in Biochemistry to map out the expository areas of gainful employment through various aspects of biochemistry. Again, the relevance of biochemical in fields of science. Engaging proficient discussants brainstorming is useful for idea transmission and ventilation of the mind (Gundumogula, 2020). With the recent advances in biochemistry, including newer technologies and equipment inventions, there are expectations of productiveness for Biochemistry graduates following the discussion outcome.

The participant should hold a Biochemistry degree and have at least 12 years of professional experience or possess a Ph.D. with a minimum of 8 years of professional experience. Participants were from either industry or tertiary institutions, and each group comprised individuals from both sectors (Table 1). The selection for participation was a proficient grasp of the thematic area relevant to the group. Exclusion criteria include unemployed graduates in Biochemistry and individuals not affiliated with Biochemistry.

Nigeria is facing severe economic hardship. That requires real live solutions, investing rightfully knowledge-wise. The war against diseases depends upon the flow of new scientific knowledge, products, industries, and jobs. Biochemistry is an effective match. Sciences are good for national welfare as a team. Biochemistry is a member of the science team. Considering the present economic hardship realities and the need for talent development in these associated uncertainties due to post-COVID-19 and subsidy removal, many graduates of biochemistry disciplines are still unemployed. This research analyses areas of relevancy from a biochemical perspective through a scientific discourse of their implications on the employability of biochemistry graduates.

Table 1: Participant’s distribution and Ranks

GP	Industry	Academia	Total
GP1	MG(2):SM(1)	AS (1)	4
GP 2	SM(2)	AS(2)	4
GP 3	MG(1)	AS(1):SL(2)	4
GP 4	SM(2)	SL(2)	4
GP 5	MG(1)	AS(1):SL(2)	4

GP=group, MG=manager, SM=Senior Manager, AS=Associate Professor, SL=Senior Lecturer,

2.0 Material and Method

The research employed five focus groups of four members in each group for intellectual engagement to brainstorm on various aspects of Biochemistry. The discussion and compilations were for one month to allow a sufficient time frame. The groups discussed the following: Group-1 (Medical Biochemistry), Group-2 (Food Biochemistry), Group-3 (Mechano-medicine), Group-4 (Industrial Biochemistry), and Group-5: Molecular basis of disease. The theme of the discussion follows the captions in each group name. How biochemistry acquired skills and knowledge positions holders in those areas are the talking point of the research.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Results

3.1.1 Group-1: Medical Biochemistry

Biochemistry is a player in elucidating the route of disease development, helping craft potential remedies, and aiding the understanding of ill health for improved health outcomes. The group opinion is that Medical sciences hinges on biochemistry. An arguable case is understanding the molecular disease basis to unmask the root source of ill health at the molecular stage, which is demystified through many biochemical perceptions by studying the chemical changes in biomolecules (Stotz and Vennesland, 2024). The dysfunctional state produces structural changes in biomolecules, and in some cases, proteins are misfolded (Sweeney et al., 2017 and Reynaud, 2010). All Structural changes in molecules are part of the disease signature, and biochemistry has aided in elucidating structures of normal and abnormal affected biomolecules due to ill health (Kozarich, 2009). Physiochemically, proteins fold correctly at minimal energy configuration (Dinner et al., 2000). Despite that, as organisms age, misfolded proteins increase susceptibility to Alzheimer's, diabetes, cancer, neurodegenerative, and other diseases (Finkel, 2005). In general,

2.1 Research criteria

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

organismal aging holds importance for human health because it increases susceptibility to many diseases (Kennedy *et al.*, 2014, Guo *et al.*, 2022, Tenchov *et al.*, 2024, and Sen *et al.*, 2016).

Hallmarks of the aging process include telomere shortening, genomic instability, epigenetic modifications, mitochondrial dysfunction, loss of proteostasis, dysregulated nutrient sensing, stem cell exhaustion, cellular senescence, and altered cellular communication (Maldonado *et al.*, 2023).

Proteins are essential for organisms because they participate in virtually every process within the cell. Misfolded (called toxic conformations) proteins are toxic, as biochemical mechanisms that control the correct folding of proteins are consequential to their proper physiological functioning (Mori *et al.*, 1993). This finding has been crucial for understanding disease origin and developing new therapies and inventions. Misfolded proteins result when a protein follows the wrong folding pathway or energy-minimizing funnel. Protein misfolding is a natural phenomenon, bound to accumulate as we age. Aging is the most risk factor for many diseases (Dillin *et al.*, 2014). Misfolded proteins are typically insoluble and tend to form long linear or fibrillar aggregates known as amyloid deposits. Regrettably, this toxic configuration can interact with other native copies of the same protein and catalyse their transition into the toxic state (Alper *et al.* 1967 and Griffith 1967). It is the infective conformations. The newly made toxic proteins repeat the cycle in a self-sustaining loop, amplifying the toxicity and thus leading to a catastrophic effect that eventually kills the cell or impairs its function (causing disease). Prion is a prime example of proteins that catalyse their conformational change into toxic form. Biochemical cell mechanisms exist to prevent proteins from folding incorrectly, getting rid of misfolding proteins. It is via the chaperone mechanism.

Despite this self-mechanism protection, protein misfolding is inevitable. The action is not perfect, but there is a remedy. The misfolded proteins can be detected by quality-control mechanisms in the cell that tag them to be sent to the cytoplasm, where they will be degraded. With biochemistry, a longer life is not a grim prospect. By utilizing knowledge from biochemistry and related fields such as molecular biology and immunology,

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

professionals in medical sciences have the potential to revolutionize global healthcare. Calling on a working knowledge of biochemistry and related disciplines - molecular biology and immunology, those working in medical sciences can transform healthcare globally. The general pattern that emerges in all these diseases is an abnormal tendency of proteins to aggregate as a result of misfolding. The aggregation can be caused by chance; by protein hyperphosphorylation (a condition where multiple phosphate groups are added to the protein), by prion self-catalytic conformational conversion, or by mutations that make the protein unstable. Severity of these diseases correlates with an increase in oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, alteration of cytoplasmic membrane permeability, and abnormal calcium concentration (Lin and Beal 2006). The idea that proteins could be infectious by themselves was highly controversial because it appeared to challenge the central dogma of molecular biology. Though counterintuitive, it is a fact.

Knowledge of biochemistry is fundamental for tackling pandemics. SARS-COV-2 that caused Covid-19, an unprecedented pandemic had biochemically revealed spiked protein called E (Deng and Baker, 2021) as aiding tool for main entering point into the host cell. Biochemical revealing features in spike glycoprotein are- 1273 amino acid residues long (Zhu *et al.*, 2021) and that, the S1 region is responsible for interacting with receptor molecules called angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) (Zhu *et al.*, 2021), present on the surface of the host cell, is the first step of viral entry (Wang, *et al.*, 2020 and Li, 2016), aside replication (Deng and Baker, 2021). Biochemical idea of mutation revealed that Spike protein part that interact with ACE2 are not likely to mutate or change. This protein-ACE2 interaction is the key for a solution breakthrough. The biochemistry put into action is the development of decoy ACE2 proteins- a protein that binds to SARS-COV-2 before it can attached to human cell. This is promising target for new treatments (Tada *et al.*, 2023). The wisdom is the expectation to prevent SARS-CoV-2 from attaching to cells. It is also unlikely that the virus will change shape in a way that makes it resistant to an ACE2 decoy, because the virus relies on ACE2 to cause infections. Particles that gum up the keys that the virus uses to enter cells could one day be an effective COVID-19 treatment

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

whenever vaccines and other treatments fall short. Biochemistry is relevant in the treatments of disease.

Considering the upsurge of public health threats such as climate change, non-communicable and infectious diseases, and antimicrobial resistance, biochemical applications are needed more than ever. Advances in biochemical knowledge leading to illuminations in many areas of medicine (diseases) have received attention. The discussion is on the selected health conditions, highlighting exciting new developments and illuminating the biochemical pathways that arrest the absurd health situation. The knowledge of biochemistry is conspicuously excellent for application on it. Many diseases- diabetes, atherosclerosis, cancer, infectious diseases, malnutrition, liver disease, and Alzheimer's disease have biochemical makers, measured in body fluids. Many biomolecules in the body are affected in structure, function, or amount in a disease state. Disease can cause deficiency or excess of affected biomolecules. A case in point is the persistent hyperglycemia. Biochemical monitoring of glucose alongside lipid profile and others in the blood are useful indexes of prognostic values in diabetes mellitus. Currently a wearable device for continuous glucose monitoring has been invented, given better hope for diabetic sufferers. Since the Biochemical perturbations that cause disease may occur rapidly or slowly, the device is helpful in proper diabetes monitoring. The biochemical markers of organ derangement could give clues for the effects a treatment has. Creatinine levels in urine and blood could be effective in assessing kidney health, in the case of nephrotic diseases. The foundation for understanding all processes of disorders is in biochemistry. It explains many bases of ill health that affect living things. Though the disease mechanism may not be the same for all living things, there is the biochemical concept. Biochemical concepts are fundamental in understanding of ill-health.

Following the concepts from biochemical features in ill health and disease processes, biochemists in the health sector can examine the possible causes and aid in disease treatments. Through biochemical parameters from laboratory test results, the Clinician's thinking per particular treatment may change for improved health outcomes. No discipline would understand

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

biochemical changes in ill health besides the knowledge from biochemistry (Silva, 2023). Clinician-patient interactions have laboratory biochemical tests support for rightful diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis. For good judgment by clinicians, discernment is natural for creating logical reasoning in the clinical setting (Milner and Malcolm, 1990).

Studies on genes from *C. elegans* and *D. melanogaster* shed light on human diseases and other indexes anchored in biochemistry. The groups exert that understanding the biochemical process in various pathological states applied intelligently in many laboratory procedures, diagnostics, and prognostics make health goals achievable. The discussions agree with Alastair (2018) on the prevailing world health and ill health conditions, with many fascinating aspects of diseases- common and rare possess biochemical phenomena. Biochemistry could right wrongs for better health diagnosis, treatment and prognosis.

3.1.2 Group-2 Food Biochemistry.

Food is for nourishment and perhaps for pleasure, religious and cultural reasons. Nutrition impacts physical and mental health, portraying close interaction among food, indigenous microbes, gut health, and many diseases (Conlon and Bird, 2014). Nutritional biochemistry is instrumental in investigating the mechanisms underlying the close associates of diet-disease interaction. Nutritional biochemistry interacts with other fields, including basic sciences and physical sciences, for knowledge in clinical nutrition, macronutrients, fuel requirements, nutritional genome nutrients, and a host of contributors to the interplay between food and disease, capable of improving cell function and metabolism. Nutrition by the discussant exertion is a shift from a balanced to an ideal diet. The primary objective is to determine the best dietary and nutritional needs for healthy people and those suffering from illness. Nutrition biochemistry aims to devise methods for minimizing the adverse effects of pharmaceutical medications. From the principles of nutrition in biochemistry. There are valuable insights on how diet influences the onset, progression, and outlook of various physical ailments (such as cancer, diabetes, heart disease, and stroke) and mental health conditions (including autism, Attention Deficit

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), anxiety, depression, dementia, and schizophrenia) can be revealed. Food is indispensable to the body. It provides energy and vital biomolecules necessary for optimal bodily functions. Poor nutrition precedes disordered physiological psychology and an exaggerated biomolecule, culminating in poor health. A nutrient is of prime importance in health, and biochemistry is the face card. The group deemed this proper and appropriate.

Food after digestion undergoes metabolism for the release of nutrient therein. Cellular metabolism involves complex biochemical processes through which specific nutrients are released (Ahmad *et al.*, 2021). Unlike normal cells, cancer cells rewire their cellular metabolism to promote growth and survival and thus have different nutritional requirements, and many different cancer types exhibit similar metabolic alterations (DeBerardinis and Thompson, 2012 and Pavlova, and Thompson, 2016). Although the exact mechanism(s) of cancer altered metabolism and its effect on cancer behaviour is not fully understood, an increased awareness of the dependencies of cancer cells on specific metabolic pathways exist. The altered metabolism fulfils the demands of increased growth and proliferation. This alteration is partly, orchestrated by the genetic changes that govern tumorigenesis (Pavlova and Thompson, 2016). Some known cancer-associated metabolic changes hallmarks are: deregulated uptake of glucose and amino acids, use of opportunistic modes of nutrient acquisition, use of glycolysis/TCA cycle intermediates for biosynthesis and NADPH production, increased demand for nitrogen, alterations in metabolite-driven gene regulation, and metabolic interactions with the microenvironment (Figure 1). Applying logic to altered metabolic dependency infers the potential for therapeutically exploiting these dependencies. There is a renewed interest for better understanding of the underlying processes. A cancer cell must increase the import of nutrients from the environment. Two principal nutrients that support survival and biosynthesis in mammalian cells are glucose and glutamine.

In glucose metabolism via glycolysis, hexokinases (HK) catalyse the essentially irreversible first step of the glycolytic pathway, and a high-level expression is associated with poor prognosis in cancer patients (Wolf *et al.*,

2021 and Mathupala *et al.*, 2001). It is the point of biochemical relevance in deciding treatment response in cancer patients. With new biochemical and molecular biological tools in cancer cell glucose metabolism, there is more understanding of the mechanisms and functional consequences of tumor-associated metabolic alterations at various stages of tumorigenesis. Many new molecular imaging techniques- mass spectroscopy and hyperpolarised carbon-13 (¹³C) MRI are in use. Mass spectroscopy has helped to quantify the carbon influx of the central metabolic pathways (examples are the TCA cycle, glycolysis, and pentose phosphate pathway) in mammalian systems. This approach has been instrumental in demonstrating tumor metabolism-dependent factors such as the tissue of origin, tumor microenvironment (TME), the level of hypoxia, and others. Hyperpolarised carbon-13 (¹³C) MRI monitors the uptake and metabolism of endogenous biomolecules. ¹³C-MRI is particularly attractive because carbon is the backbone for nearly all organic molecules, thus allowing the investigation of more biochemical processes relevant to human disease. Carbon's unique information on tissue biochemistry is very informative (Deen *et al.*, 2023). The high utilization of extracellular glucose and glutamine by cancer cells results in extracellular lactate accumulation, which affects several cell types within the tumor microenvironment. Increased lactate levels promote the emergence of an immune-permissive microenvironment by attenuating dendritic and T cell activation and monocyte migration (Fischer *et al.*, 2007, Goetze *et al.*, 2011, Gottfried *et al.*, 2006). More so, lactate stimulates the polarization of resident macrophages to a so-called M2 state, which plays a role in immunosuppression (Carmona-Fontaine *et al.*, 2013, Colegio *et al.*, 2014).

Again, increased lactate levels stimulate hyaluronic acid production by fibroblasts, which may contribute to tumor invasiveness (Stern *et al.*, 2002). Lactic acid accumulations intensify acidity and favor cancer cells. Nutrition rich in an alkaline diet is a probable part of treatment protocols. How cancer cells reprogram their microenvironment to assist tumor growth and dissemination is an area of intense investigation. Such reprogramming encompasses multiple strategies, among which are secreted growth factors and alterations to the extracellular matrix and cell-cell interactions. Above all, aging (Figure

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2), excess caloric intake, and obesity are a factor in cancer menace. Many diseases may be associated with undernourishment or overnourishment. Malnutrition by consensus of group opinion skewed to over nutrition. More people are likely to suffer ill health due to overnutrition than undernutrition. Discussants theorized that more people fall under high BMI than low BMI. Many may not feel right based on not eating rightly. The constituents of food, when broken down and assimilated within the body, consist of macronutrients (such as carbohydrates, fats, and proteins) for energy provision, alongside micronutrients (vitamins and minerals) needed in small amounts. Eating right in the right combination is achievable from the biochemical-led knowledge. A nutritional biochemist strives to enhance community health by alleviating malnutrition or scrutinizing the nutrition elements. It could be in diseases such as diabetes or obesity, whether in surplus or inadequate amounts, may impact the human body. Emphatic acceptance of the incurability of diabetes and other chronic illnesses exists. Drugs are helpful, but they will progress. It appears like shifting the evil days with drugs. Appropriate food and others might reverse diabetes. Biochemistry of nutrition considers food rich in fiber, low glycaemic and carbohydrate load indexes, plus feeding times and intermittent fasting to improve insulin actions.

Nutritional biochemistry advocates for mindful food choices alongside portion size controls to demonstrate diabetic remission (reversion). Proper dietary measures enhance improvement in overall health. These would cause less economic stress on the sufferers. A biochemist in this field is also required to engage in the development of novel crops or the enhancement of crops to bolster human health. Defining dietary regulations for the general public is part of the essentialities of nutritional biochemistry. Nutrition biochemistry holds substantial real-world implications, capable of shaping the trajectory of preventable diseases in the future. A case in point is Carbohydrates' role in the health and functioning of the gut, and they can undergo digestion by the microbiota in the large intestine (Cummings and Stephen, 2007). From a biochemical perspective, individuals at either extreme of the nutrition spectrum face heightened risks: those who are overweight have an increased likelihood of succumbing to degenerative diseases in middle age, whereas the underweight is more prone to

premature death from infectious conditions (Kim *et al.*, 2019). In addition to a balanced diet, a diverse range of foods provides the optimal source of vital vitamins and minerals (Ward, 2014).

Figure 1: The emerging hallmarks of cancer metabolism (Pavlova and Thompson, 2016).

Fig. 2. The link between aging and cancer. The potential causes of age-associated cancer (Havas et al., 2022)

3.1.3 Group-3: Mechano-medicine

Mechano-medicine aids the understanding of molecular and cellular responses of individuals and collective cells, tissue, organs, and systems by mechanical stimuli. The knowledge gained is

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strategic to health improvement. Focusing on pathology to align mechano-medicine in various diseases following biochemical endowment is advantageous in addressing health issues. A probe on the molecular processes accounting for changes in cell metabolism that precede the physiological adaptation of living cells in response to perturbation is biochemistry from group exertion. Biochemistry prompts the promotion through numerous vital biological processes, which operate with seemingly minimal quantities of molecules, sparking a renewed focus on the effects of noise, discomfort, stress, pain, tension and other factors. Tensional homeostasis is a testament to how living organisms adjust to optimize their efficiency across various physiological functions. The myocardium harbors a range of mechanosensitive channels, as noted by Bustamante *et al.* (1991). By undergoing contraction and expansion, myocardial tissues initiate a mechano-chemical process, leading to ionic alterations that influence the phases of contraction and expansion. Also, biomechanical cues are ubiquitous to embryonic development and regulation of the mechano-chemical homeostasis of adult organs. Deviations from these homeostases are causing diseases. Human bodies are exposed continuously to mechanical stimuli, such as elastic-dynamic stimuli that act on the heart, including stretch and shear stress, as well as fluid-dynamic stimuli that act on blood vessels, including shear stress and hydrostatic pressure resulting from blood flow (Naruse, 2018a). Each structure that forms the heart seems to be a device that senses mechanical stimuli, including the extracellular matrix, focal adhesion complexes, lipid bilayers, and cellular orientation. Each of these structures plays a role in mechanotransduction.

In addition, numerous proteins are involved in mechanotransduction, including integrins, Rho kinase, PI3K, integrin-linked kinase, focal adhesion kinase, Src, extracellular signal-regulated kinase, MAP kinase, eNOS, and others. These proteins are involved in cellular mechanotransduction pathways that mediate various heart responses, including arrhythmias, hypertrophy, and ischaemic heart disease. Their conformational changes are in response to mechanical stimuli. Mechanical forces are regulators of biology and disease. Cardiac muscle cells have an intrinsic ability to sense and respond to mechanical load through a process known as

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mechanotransduction. In the heart, this process involves the conversion of mechanical stimuli into biochemical events that induce changes in myocardial structure and function. Mechanotransduction and its downstream effects function as adaptive responses that serve as compensatory mechanisms during adaptation to the initial load. However, under prolonged and abnormal loading conditions, the remodeling processes can become maladaptive, leading to altered physiological function and the development of pathological cardiac hypertrophy and heart failure (Lyon *et al.*, 2015). Specific protein complexes linked with mechanotransduction and mechanotransmission within the sarcomere, the intercalated disc, and the sarcolemma have been uncovered. The protein structures acting as mechanotransducers are the first step in the process that drives physiological and pathological cardiac hypertrophy and remodeling, as well as the transition to heart failure, and may provide better insights into mechanisms driving mechanotransduction-based diseases (Lyon *et al.*, 2015).

The heart's ability to maintain homeostasis after illness could be compromised while in the process. The disruption of homeostasis is a precursor to pathological conditions. A potential remedy for the disorder involves adjusting the tension back to its normal homeostatic levels. This approach falls within the realm of mechano-medicine. Many non-drug therapies, such as in African traditional medicine (bone setting, acupuncture, others) and pulmonary resuscitation, are typical forms of mechano-medicine application. These therapies are effective, cheap, and convenient. The fundamental mechanisms behind the efficacy of these esteemed treatments and approaches are novel. Mechano-medicine may provide an approach to uncovering these secrets.

The group posits that individual molecular occurrences can yield significant observable outcomes at a macroscopic level within biological systems. An illustrative example is the retention of genetic data within a solitary DNA strand, where alterations in the configuration of a lone molecule (mutations) can impact physiological processes and the overall physiology of successive generations. Another intriguing aspect involves biochemical signaling molecules engaging with their receptors via kinetic

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

processes, resulting in an equilibrium between bound and unbound states. Here, variations in the occupation of a binding site represent thermal noise (William and Sima, 2005). Typically, homeostasis refers to the balance of chemical and thermal factors like temperature, blood pH, and glucose concentration. Recent research has indicated that disruptions in mechanical equilibrium are a risk to various diseases, including irregular wound healing, developmental irregularities, and cancer (Han *et al.*, 2020). It is a less-known aspect of homeostasis. Essential signaling molecules, whether originating externally or internally, exist in limited quantities, and their levels dictate the functioning of downstream biochemical networks, which are pivotal to cellular activities (William and Sima, 2005). Through mechano-medicine, the physiology and pathology of life can go back to the basics of health. It is scalable and integrates with the multilevel pathologic states, enabling highly parallelized studies and the development of new therapies.

Mechano-medicine has the potential to unravel cancer treatment. The innovative tools-microfluidic devices contribute to identifying several overarching mechanisms involved in cancer progressions, such as angiogenesis, tumor growth, and metastasis, and are mechano-medicine tools. Mechano-medicine will emerge as a bridge between mechanobiology and the biomedical field. Naruse (2018b) opinions reconsideration studies on diagnoses and treatment of various diseases, with mechano-medicine integrated for the ultimate survival of man from problems that confront humans.

3.1.4 Group-4: Industrial Biochemistry

Biochemistry plays a central role in contemporary biomedical research, aiding in the development and formulation of drugs. Industrial uses encompass large-scale detergent production, para-medical product manufacturing, analytical applications such as biosensors and medical spot-tests, agriculture applications like phytomedicine and antimycotic agents, production of biopolymers for medical and food sectors, petrochemistry tasks including acrylonitrile production and enzyme application in refinery processes (biorefining), and the production of biomethane and bioethanol from agro-food waste for biofuel generation.

Enzymes have industrial applications. Recent biochemical advancements of significance involve cell fusion, genetic engineering, nucleic acid techniques, and protein order and synthesis. The depiction of protein structure provides insight into understanding the molecular foundation of enzyme catalysis. These discoveries have facilitated the isolation and manufacturing of novel therapeutic proteins, exploration of innovative biocatalysis methods for enhanced diagnostic protocols, cultivation of new plant species and biomaterials, and advancement in plant protection techniques. Enzymes play a crucial role in various processes in the food industry. Enzymes of relevance and importance can be produced through microbial fermentation or genetically modified organisms (GMOs) (Jackson *et al.*, 2019). For enzyme extraction, a suitable culture medium follows the extraction and purification of the target enzyme (Ananthkrishnan and Ehrlicher, 2007). In the case of GMOs, genetic engineering techniques introduce specific genes into organisms to produce enzymes of interest (Michie and Löwe 2006). These biochemical processes could enhance food production and develop innovative chemicals.

In this way, biochemistry continues to revolutionize industrial sectors, fostering advancements in sustainability, safety, and overall product quality (Maglaveras *et al.*, 1998). Enzymes extractable from fruits and honey: pineapple- Bromelain (Pavan *et al.*, 2012), papayas- papain (Muss *et al.*, 2013), mangoes- amylase (Adebiyi *et al.*, 2002), and honey- amylases and glucosidases (Burlando *et al.*, 2013) have several benefits (treatment of angina pectoris, bronchitis, sinusitis, surgical trauma, and thrombophlebitis, debridement of wounds, and enhanced absorption of drugs, control of pain, edema, anticancerous activities and promotes apoptotic cell death, ease digestive) Pavan *et al.*, 2012, Stremnitzer *et al.*, 2013 and de Souza *et al.*, 2019). Their biochemical values are on an industrial scale.

Furthermore, they have initiated efforts to harness biological systems more effectively for hazardous waste management and sustainable utilization of natural resources. These discoveries have facilitated the isolation and manufacturing of novel therapeutic proteins, exploration of innovative biocatalysis methods for enhanced

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

diagnostic protocols, cultivation of new plant species and biomaterials, and advancement in plant protection techniques. The rapid progress in biochemistry findings has sparked fresh opportunities for job creation in industrial biotechnology. These prospects pertain to the potential employment opportunities for recent biochemistry graduates in industries focused on human healthcare, agriculture, chemicals, and environmental sectors. The challenges revolve around the transformation of scientific discoveries into practical technological applications. The unemployment or nonskilled employment of Biochemists will drastically reduce. The recent biochemical technologies can force the development of advanced manufacturing processes capable of getting unemployed youth off the street. It is a clean-up using biochemical knowledge. The sense of discussion is to reposition biochemistry, and there is a sense in this.

3.1.5 Group-5 Molecular basis of disease.

Biochemistry is vital to modern medicine, and with biochemistry, better medications are designed and tested for disease treatment. It is all about health improvement. The increase in life expectancy of humans is not by accident but a certifiable responsibility of the field of biochemistry. The diverse disease manifestation demands the signature embedded in the knowledge obtainable in biochemistry. It is a nerve center in health analyses, and biochemistry is a personified mythical figure.

The molecular basis of health, disease development, and progression is unachievable by a single discipline. Long-term disease complications like diabetes cause untold damage to large arteries and capillaries following a protracted period of high blood sugar concentrations above the normal range (10 Mmol/L). The biochemical interpretation might be that the exposed proteins and lipids modifications from the non-enzymatic process consequent to protracted high sugar concentration are the process. The advanced glycation end-product formation is the culprit in the disease process. Another biochemical factor at play is oxidative stress, which causes damage to the vascular endothelium, the lining of blood vessels, due to protracted high sugar levels. The amount of glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) from red blood

cells gives the extent. This is a retrospective biochemical diagnostic test for diabetes. It is a valuable assessment of hyperglycemia over three months, reflecting the lifespan of a red blood cell (The duration of a red blood cell's life is approximately 120 days). Though all Life sciences are crucial in disease understanding, Biochemistry has its virtual presence in all life sciences. Notably, the group is not in any way arrogating the molecular basis of disease to biochemistry alone, but biochemistry is central to all life sciences. It provides insight into understanding and managing health and disease to improve treatment outcomes. The expectance is a rationalized drug design and others for managing ill health.

Treatment of chronic health disorders such as cancer disease by apoptosis requires careful attention to the molecular basis of the disease. Cancer is a fundamental disorder in regulating cell proliferation and differentiation, resulting from genetic changes that lead to the loss of normal regulation within the affected cells. The remarkable rate of advancement in Biochemistry emphasizes cellular and molecular biology, facilitating comprehension of the underlying causes of cancer and offering improved strategies for prevention and treatment. Biochemistry is an efficient tool for a better understanding of cancer mechanisms. There is no doubt that cancer continues to present a significant global threat to public health. Biochemistry reveals bioactive phytochemicals of saponins (ginsenosides) and other variants contained in Ginseng and other herbs as an attestable remedy for cancer disease. Numerous biochemistry laboratory-based studies of the anti-cancer properties of ginsenosides revealed they compel tumor cells to undergo programmed cell death. As a consequence, cancer cell growth halts. Grasping the intricacies of the cell cycle is crucial for unraveling many mechanisms implicated in the formation and advancement of cancer checkpoints. It ensures that each stage in the cell cycle is executed accurately and prevents incompletely replicated DNA from being transmitted to daughter cells. Notably, it is relevant because anti-cancer drugs specifically target cells undergoing division or are likely in a particular phase of the cell cycle. The functions of different cyclin-dependent kinases (CDKs), cyclins, and other relevant molecules that influence the cell cycle (such as the RB and P53 genes) can be extensively understood from a

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

biochemical standpoint. Biochemistry by group exertion is a contrivance to fool the cancer disease.

Apoptosis genetically is a regulated program. The activation triggers cell death. The primary proteins responsible for apoptosis, known as proteolytic enzymes (caspases), are biochemical compounds in an inactive state (procaspases). The entirety of apoptosis is a multifaceted process. It is a closely regulated biochemical process. Certain proteins serve as receptors and adaptors, procaspases and caspases, alongside the pro- and anti-apoptotic factors. All these biochemical entities are participants, and the mitochondria participate in the necessary death of the cell. Notably, there are mechanisms by cancer cells promoting evadable apoptosis and thus unceasing growth and division. Biochemically, these mechanisms encompass mutations leading to the loss of protein function, which may trigger apoptosis or the overexpression of anti-apoptotic genes. The functional loss of the P53 gene is probably the most common cancer-mutated gene. Biochemically, there is a resultant upregulation of pro-apoptotic proteins with balance shifts in the balance toward anti-apoptotic proteins. Elevated levels of anti-apoptotic genes are observed in cancers. The resulting evasion of apoptosis favors the continuing growth of cancers. Though Apoptosis goes through various developmental and physiological processes, biochemistry gives directions to a better understanding. Paradoxically, controlled cell death is essential for maintaining health by facilitating the formation of new cells. Aside from cancer, this apoptosis has implications for other diseases. This encompasses specific autoimmune and chronic neurological conditions, like Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases, where an excess of cell death, as opposed to excessive cell growth, is a characteristic. Cancer arises from unregulated growth and proliferation, where cells have evaded the normal growth control mechanism and divide incessantly. It is a complex process that unfolds over multiple stages, necessitating numerous genetic alterations with time.

The ground-breaking advancements in cellular and molecular biochemistry have opened up an unparalleled opportunity for scientific approaches to comprehend cancer development and progression (Choi *et al.*, 2013). These novel advancements and the knowledge gained

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significantly impact the clinical aspects of cancer prevention, disease management, and treatment of malignancies. Despite these scientific advancements, challenges persist in fully understanding the intricate nature of cancer, including issues related to disease recurrence, drug resistance, and other factors. Therefore, it is imperative to prioritize biochemical pathways contributing to cancer development to enhance our understanding of human health. Through cancer-related biochemical pathways, cancerous tissue contains the same enzymes or other biochemical components as those found in normal tissues. Knowledge of biochemistry highlights the distinctions between cancerous and noncancerous cells, which can be attributable to changes in the relative amounts or activities of specific biochemical components. Biochemical discovery is reporting a potential biochemical basis for the apparent cancer-fighting ability of broccoli and its veggie cousins. Specific compounds found in vegetables can target and inhibit a faulty gene linked to cancer. This discovery could pave the way for a novel approach to cancer prevention and treatment.

Despite our understanding of its pathogenesis, the exact cause of rheumatoid arthritis, an inflammatory joint disease, remains unknown. Rheumatoid arthritis patients often exhibit specific antibodies known as rheumatoid factors, which target the Fc portion of other antibody molecules, thereby amplifying inflammatory responses. The ongoing research on rheumatoid factors, employing molecular cloning techniques, holds promise for insights extending beyond rheumatoid arthritis. In patients with rheumatoid arthritis, significant attention is in investigating interactions between T lymphocytes and cells in the joint lining. T-lymphocytes engage with other cells through cell contact-mediated mechanisms and the production of cytokines such as interleukin 1, tumor necrosis factor, lymphotoxin, transforming growth factors, platelet-derived growth factor, and specific colony-stimulatory factors. These interactions may lead to the proliferation of joint lining cells, resulting in fibrosis and the production of proteinases and lipid metabolites (prostaglandins and leukotrienes) responsible for joint swelling and pain. A comprehensive study of proteinases and cytokines is essential for identifying potential new targets for therapeutic intervention.

3.2 Discussion

Human and natural resource endowments make Nigeria a potential player in the world economy. However, this potential has remained relatively unexploited for many years. With the greater dependence on crude oil and gas following the shift from the agricultural sector in the late 1960s, Nigeria continued to ride on consumption.

The molecular basis of diseases alongside nutritional, mechano-medicine, industrial, and medical biochemistry was the focus to portray the extent biochemistry could imply in economic development. Since biochemistry has many applications, it allows members to have a vast area to work (Figure 1). The valid points in the research were the following: modern biochemical techniques applied to agriculture could improve the quality and quantity of food sufficient to adequately feed the national population and create a surplus for export to continental and international markets, biochemical advances in numerous health conditions, knowledge of the biochemical basis of disease, uncovering the causes of pathologies, and monitoring disease on a cellular level are advancements, all leading to curing diseases. Biochemistry has made a giant stride in drug discovery, disease models, functional assays, gene expression analysis, and protein structure determination.

Biochemistry is transformative with pedagogical approaches and experiential learning. Biochemistry is much more than a singular, uniform field of study. All the applications in biochemistry are tools for work creation and gainful employment for holders of biochemistry disciplines and allies. Biochemistry serves as the basis for various other scientific fields. Why students studying biochemistry are oblivious to the place of biochemistry in the industrial markets may be partly responsible for the many unemployed graduates of Biochemistry. Biochemistry is the ugly ducklings.

Figure 1: Varieties of work place employability graduates of Biochemistry discipline.

4.0 Conclusion

Setting the beginner in the Biochemistry discipline to the basics is a good starter. Food digestion, energy production, new agents to cure cancer and others, allergic reactions, coagulation complexes, and how the body carries oxygen, blood types, and antibodies are fascinating aspects of biochemistry. Overall, biochemistry is a foundational science that underpins many aspects of human health, medicine and economy, playing a critical role in understanding, economic diagnosing, and treating various diseases and conditions.

What is necessary is the recognition of the Biochemistry niche in societies (Nigeria and other nations) and to let the game start. This idea expressed in the research is not a tall story written with ostentatious admiration/pride in Biochemistry but rather uncovering realities.

Solitary Author

Conflict of Interest

There was no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgement

Body: The discussant gave out their precious time for this exercise, indeed I am grateful to all the discussants members of each group. The researcher acknowledges the effort of all, for their contribution is huge.

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

References

hypertrophy. *Journal of Cardiovascular Pharmacology*, 17(Suppl 2):S110-S113. doi: 10.1097/00005344-199117002-00024.

- Adebiyi, A., Adaikan, P. G., & Prasad, R. N. (2002). Papaya (*Carica papaya*) consumption is unsafe in pregnancy: fact or fable? Scientific evaluation of a common belief in some parts of Asia using a rat model. *The British journal of nutrition*, 88(2), 199–203. <https://doi.org/10.1079/BJNBJN200259>
- Ahmad F., Cherukuri, K. M. & Choyke, P. L. (2021). Metabolic reprogramming in prostate cancer *British Journal of Cancer* 125:1185–1196; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41416-021-01435-5>
- Alastair J. B. (2018). The biochemical basis of disease. *Essays Biochem.* 62 (5): 619–642. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1042/EBC20170054>
- Alper, T., Cramp, W. A, Haig, D. A, & Clarke, M. C. ((1967). Does the Agent of Scrapie Replicate without Nucleic Acid? *Nature* 214, 764–766 <https://doi.org/10.1038/214764a0>.
- Ananthakrishnan, R., & Ehrlicher, A. (2007). The forces behind cell movement. *International journal of biological sciences*, 3(5), 303–317. <https://doi.org/10.7150/ijbs.3.303>
- Bialek, W. & Setayeshgar, S. (2005). Physical limits to biochemical signaling. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 102(29), 10040–10045. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0504321102>
- Burlando, B., & Cornara, L. (2013). Honey in dermatology and skin care: a review. *Journal of cosmetic dermatology*, 12(4), 306–313. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.12058>.
- Bustamante, J. O., Ruknudin, A. & Sachs, F. (1991). Stretch-activated channels in heart cells: relevance to cardiac hypertrophy. *Journal of Cardiovascular Pharmacology*, 17(Suppl 2):S110-S113. doi: 10.1097/00005344-199117002-00024.
- Carmona-Fontaine, C., Bucci, V., Akkari, L., Deforet, M., Joyce, J. A., & Xavier, J. B. (2013). Emergence of spatial structure in the tumor microenvironment due to the Warburg effect. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 110(48), 19402–19407. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1311939110>
- Choi, J. S., Chun, K. S., Kundu, J., & Kundu, J. K. (2013). Biochemical basis of cancer chemoprevention and/or chemotherapy with ginsenosides (Review). *International Journal of Molecular Medicine*, 32(6):1227-38. doi: [10.3892/ijmm.2013.1519](https://doi.org/10.3892/ijmm.2013.1519)
- Colegio, O. R., Chu, N. Q., Szabo, A. L., Chu, T., Rhebergen, A. M., Jairam, V., Cyrus, N., Brokowski, C. E., Eisenbarth, S. C., Phillips, G. M., Cline, G. W., Phillips, A. J., & Medzhitov, R. (2014). Functional polarization of tumour-associated macrophages by tumour-derived lactic acid. *Nature*, 513(7519), 559–563. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13490>
- Conlon, M. A., & Bird, A. R. (2014). The impact of diet and lifestyle on gut microbiota and human health. *Nutrients*, 7(1), 17–44. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu7010017>
- Cummings, J. H. & Stephen, A. M. (2007). Carbohydrate terminology and classification. *Eur J Clin Nutr.* 61 Suppl 1:S5-18. doi: 10.1038/sj.ejcn.1602936
- DeBerardinis, R. J., & Thompson, C. B. (2012). Cellular metabolism and disease: what do metabolic outliers teach us?. *Cell*, 148(6), 1132–1144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2012.02.032>
- Deen, S. S., Rooney, C., Shinozaki, A., McGing, J., Grist, J. T., Tyler, D. J., Serrão, E., &

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

- Gallagher, F. A. (2023). Hyperpolarized Carbon 13 MRI: Clinical Applications and Future Directions in Oncology. *Radiology. Imaging cancer*, 5(5), e230005.
<https://doi.org/10.1148/rycan.230005>
- Deng, X. & Baker, S.C. (2021). Coronaviruses: Molecular Biology (Coronaviridae. Encyclopedia of Virology: 198–207.
[doi:10.1016/](https://doi.org/10.1016/)
- Dillin, A., Gottschling, D. E., & Nystrom, T. (2014). The good and the bad of being connected: the integrons of aging. *Current opinion in cell biology*, 26, 107–112.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceb.2013.12.003>
- Dinner, A. R., Sali, A., Smith, L. J., Dobson, C. M., & Karplus, M. (2000). Understanding protein folding via free-energy surfaces from theory and experiment. *Trends in biochemical sciences*, 25(7), 331–339.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s09680004\(00\)01610-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s09680004(00)01610-8)
- Finkel, T. (2005). Radical medicine: Treating ageing to cure disease. *Nature Reviews Molecular Cell Biology* 6, 971–976 DOI <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrm1763>.
- Fischer, K., Hoffmann, P., Voelkl, S., Meidenbauer, N., Ammer, J., Edinger, M., Gottfried, E., Schwarz, S., Rothe, G., Hoves, S., Renner, K., Timischl, B., Mackensen, A., Kunz-Schughart, L., Andreesen, R., Krause, S. W., & Kreutz, M. (2007). Inhibitory effect of tumor cell-derived lactic acid on human T cells. *Blood*, 109(9), 3812–3819.
<https://doi.org/10.1182/>
- Goetze, K., Walenta, S., Ksiazkiewicz, M., Kunz-Schughart, L. A., & Mueller-Klieser, W. (2011). Lactate enhances motility of tumor cells and inhibits monocyte migration and cytokine release. *International journal of oncology*, 39(2), 453–463.
<https://doi.org/10.3892/ijo.2011.1055>
- Gottfried, E., Kunz-Schughart, L. A., Ebner, S., Mueller-Klieser, W., Hoves, S., Andreesen, R., Mackensen, A., & Kreutz, M. (2006). Tumor-derived lactic acid modulates dendritic cell activation and antigen expression. *Blood*, 107(5), 2013–2021.
<https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2005-05-1795>
- Griffith, J. (1967). Nature of the Scrapie Agent: Self-replication and Scrapie. *Nature* 215, 1043–1044 (1967).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/2151043a0>
- Guo, J., Huang, X., Dou, L., Yan, M., Shen, T., Tang W. & Li J., (2022). Aging and aging-related diseases: from molecular mechanisms to interventions and treatments. *Sig Transduct Target Ther* 7, 391 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-022-01251-0>
- Gundumogula, M. (2020). Importance of Focus Groups in Qualitative Research. *The International Journal of Humanities & Social Studies*, 8(11).
<https://doi.org/10.24940/theijhss/2020/v8/i11/HS2011-082>
- Han, Y. L., Pegoraro, A. F., Li, H., Li, K., Yuan, Y., Xu, G., Gu, Z., Sun, J., Hao, Y., Gupta, S. K., Li, Y., Tang, W., Kang, H., Teng, L., Fredberg, J. J. & Guo, M. (2020). Cell swelling, softening and invasion in a three-dimensional breast cancer model, *Nature Physics*, vol. 16, pp. 101–108.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41567-019-0680-8>
- Havas, A., Yin, S. & Adams, P. (2022). The role of aging in cancer *Molecular Oncology* 16(18):3213-3219 DOI: [10.1002/1878-0261.13302](https://doi.org/10.1002/1878-0261.13302)
- Iaria, A., Schwarz, C. & Waldinger, F. (2018). Frontier Knowledge and Scientific Production: Evidence from the Collapse of International Science, *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 133(2): 927–991.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjx046>

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

- Kennedy, B. K., Berger, S. L., Brunet, A., Campisi, J., Cuervo, A. M., Epel, E. S., Franceschi, C., Lithgow, G. J., Morimoto, R. I., Pessin, J. E., Rando, T. A., Richardson, A., Schadt, E. E., Wyss-Coray, T., & Sierra, F. (2014). Geroscience: linking aging to chronic disease. *Cell*, 159(4), 709–713. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2014.10.039>
- Kim, M. Basharat, A., Santosh, R., Mehdi, S. F., Razvi, Z., Yoo, S. K., Lowell, B., Kumar A, Brima W, Danoff A, Dankner R, Bergman M, Pavlov V. A, Yang, H. & Roth, J. (2019). Reuniting overnutrition and undernutrition, macronutrients, and micronutrients. *Diabetes / Metabolism Research and Review*, 35(1):e3072. doi: 10.1002/dmrr.3072.
- Kozarich J. W. (2009). The biochemistry of disease: desperately seeking syzygy. *Annual review of biochemistry*, 78, 55–63. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-biochem-120108-082254>
- Li, F. (2016). Structure, Function, and Evolution of Coronavirus Spike Proteins. *Annual Review of Virology*. 3 (1): 237–261. [doi:10.1146/annurev-virology-110615-042301](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-virology-110615-042301)
- Lin, M. T., and Beal, M. F. (2006). Mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress in neurodegenerative diseases. *Nature*, 443(7113), 787–795. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature05292>
- Lyon, R. C., Zanella, F., Omens, J. H., & Sheikh, F. (2015). Mechanotransduction in cardiac hypertrophy and failure. *Circulation research*, 116(8), 1462–1476. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.116.304937>
- Maglaveras, N., Stamkopoulos, T., Diamantaras, K., Pappas, C., & Srintzis, M. (1998). ECG pattern recognition and classification using non-linear transformations and neural networks: a review. *International journal of medical informatics*, 52(1-3), 191–208. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1386-5056\(98\)00138-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1386-5056(98)00138-5)
- Maldonado, E., Morales-Pison, S., Urbina, F. & Solari, A. (2023). Aging Hallmarks and the Role of Oxidative Stress. *Antioxidants*. 12, 651. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox12030651>
- Mathupala, S. P., Rempel, A., & Pedersen, P. L. (2001). Glucose catabolism in cancer cells: identification and characterization of a marked activation response of the type II hexokinase gene to hypoxic conditions. *The Journal of biological chemistry*, 276(46), 43407–43412. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M108181200>
- Michie, K. A., & Löwe, J. (2006). Dynamic filaments of the bacterial cytoskeleton. *Annual review of biochemistry*, 75, 467–492. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.biochem.75.103004.142452>
- Milner, M. A. & Malcolm, N. S. (1990) Critical thinking in the nursing curriculum. *Nurs Health Care*. 11:67–73. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2314648/>
- Mori, K., Ma, W, Gething, M. J. and Sambrook J. (1993). A transmembrane protein with a cdc2+/CDC28-related kinase activity is required for signaling from the ER to the nucleus. *Cell*. 74(4):743-756. doi: 10.1016/0092-8674(93)90521-q. PMID: 8358794.
- Muss, C., Mosgoeller, W., & Endler, T. (2013). Papaya preparation (Caricol®) in digestive disorders. *Neuro endocrinology letters*, 34(1), 38–46. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23524622/>
- Naruse, K. (2018b). Mechanomedicine. *Biophysical Review* 10, 1257–1262. doi:

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12551-018-0459-7>.

Naruse K. (2018a). MECHANOMEDICINE: applications of mechanobiology to medical sciences and next-generation medical technologies. *Journal of smooth muscle research = Nihon Heikatsukin Gakkai kikanishi*, 54(0), 83–90. <https://doi.org/10.1540/jsmr.54.83>

Pavan, R., Jain, S., Shraddha, & Kumar, A. (2012). Properties and therapeutic application of bromelain: a review. *Biotechnology research international*, 2012, 976203. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/976203>

Peter, J. Evans, M. D., Truninger, M., Meah, A. M., and Baptista, J. A. (2019). Jackson, Peter. The multiple ontologies of freshness in the UK and Portuguese agri food sectors. *Trans Inst Br Geogr*. 44, 79-93. doi: 10.1111/tran.12260

Pavlova, N. N. & Thompson, C. B. (2016). The Emerging Hallmarks of Cancer Metabolism. *Cell metabolism*, 23(1), 27–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2015.12.006>

Reynaud, E. (2010). Protein Misfolding and Degenerative Diseases. *Nature Education* 3(9):28. <https://www.nature.com/scitable/topicpage/protein-misfolding-and-degenerative-diseases-14434929/>

Sen, P., Shah, P. P., Nativio, R., & Berger, S. L. (2016). Epigenetic Mechanisms of Longevity and Aging. *Cell*, 166(4), 822–839. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2016.07.050>

Silva C (2023) Exploring the Role of Clinical Biochemistry in Disease Diagnosis and Management: Current Trends and Future Directions. *Ann Clin Lab Res*. Vol.11 No.2:458 doi: 10.36648/2386-5180.23.11.458.

Singh, P., Batra, H.S., & Naithani, M. (2004). History of biochemistry. *Bulletin of the Indian Institute of History of Medicine (Hyderabad)*, 34(1):75-86. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17152615/>

Stern, R., Shuster, S., Neudecker, B. A., & Formby, B. (2002). Lactate stimulates fibroblast expression of hyaluronan and CD44: the Warburg effect revisited. *Experimental cell research*, 276(1), 24–31. <https://doi.org/10.1006/excr.2002.5508>

Stotz, H. & Vennesland, B. (2024). biochemistry. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/science/biochemistry>

Stremnitzer, C., Manzano-Szalai, K., Willensdorfer, A., Starkl, P., Pieper, M., König, P., Mildner, M., Tschachler, E., Reichart, U. & Jensen-Jarolim, E. (2015). Papain Degrades Tight Junction Proteins of Human Keratinocytes In Vitro and Sensitizes C57BL/6 Mice via the Skin Independent of its Enzymatic Activity or TLR4 Activation. *The Journal of investigative dermatology*, 135(7), 1790–1800. <https://doi.org/10.1038/jid.2015.5>

Sweeney, P., Park, H., Baumann, M., Dunlop, J., Frydman, J., Kopito, R., McCampbell, A., Leblanc, G., Venkateswaran, A., Nurmi, A., & Hodgson, R. (2017). Protein misfolding in neurodegenerative diseases: implications and strategies. *Translational neurodegeneration*, 6, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40035-017-0077-5>

Tada, T., Minnee, J., & Landau, N. R. (2023). Vectored immunoprophylaxis and treatment of SARS-CoV-2 infection in a preclinical model. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 120(23), e2303509120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2303509120>

